

Training Kit

A guide on organising prototyping series for OpenSource healthcare innovation.

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careables.org

Table of Content

Management Summary	4
Introduction	6
The personalisation of healthcare	6
Careables: what, why, for whom	6
The training kit: how it works	7
The process in 3 phases	7
Phase 1: Preparing the prototyping series	9
2. Open Call: finding participants	9
3. Engagement: creating a community	10
4. Preparations: the prototyping sessions	12
5. Documentation: two types explained	14
Phase 2: Guiding the prototyping series	16
1. Welcome: introductions and getting started	17
2. Research: the challenge, users and solutions	19
3. Concept development: working on a solution	20
4. Prototyping I: prototyping and presenting ideas	21
5. Prototyping II: prototyping and documenting	22
6. Exposition: presenting the final products	23
Phase 3: Reflecting on the prototyping series	24
1. Reflection: evaluating the prototyping series	24
2. Sharing lessons: how to continue	24
Final general advise	24
Different formats for a similar process	24
Do's and Don'ts	25
APPENDIX 1 // Role clarification (advanced)	27
APPENDIX 2 // Assignment 1	29
APPENDIX 3 // Assignment 2	29
APPENDIX 4 // Assignment 3	30

APPENDIX 5 // Design Brief	31
APPENDIX 6 // Concept development tool	33
APPENDIX 7 // Progress document template	34
APPENDIX 8 // Instruction document template	35
APPENDIX 9 // OpenDOT Manifesto for HealthCare Codesign .	36
APPENDIX 10 // Open Call Questionnaire	38
APPENDIX 11 // Design Process Templates from HACKademy .	41
APPENDIX 12 // Team Process Templates from HACKademy .	44
APPENDIX 13 // Healthcare co-design toolkit	46

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Management Summary

Careables.org is an online platform serving as a central hub for sharing knowledge for reproduction and self-creation of customized healthcare solutions. It encompasses a repository for the storage of open hardware projects' technical documentation. It also represents an environment where individuals with particular needs, caregivers, healthcare professionals, makers and designers, share their experiences online in order to create custom-made healthcare solutions – careables.

Still, knowing what careables are and where to find them does not fully get people engaged in this type of innovation just yet. In order to get people together, share knowledge, skills and experiences, and finally create healthcare solutions additional information and guidance is necessary. Our experiences from two years of creating careables has shown us that the online infrastructure should be complemented by a well structured and personal process of programmed collaboration. This document gives insights into how the process of collaborative production of open healthcare products can be facilitated.

This Careables Training Kit is based on three main phases that we identify in the process of prototyping healthcare solutions: Preparation, Guidance, Reflection. These phases are core elements of any collaborative process and especially important for the production and replication of careables. In the preparation section we give guidelines on how to attract participants and establish partnerships with support organisations. We also present details on how to prepare the co-design sessions from a very practical perspective, such as assigning clearly defined roles and rules for collaboration. The section on guidance includes a series of templates to structure the sessions and perform specific group activities. Finally, reflection is an important element of the process as it gives participants the option to critically analyse their outcomes and share lessons learned.

The ambition and goal of this document is to make the practice of creating user centered open healthcare solutions accessible and replicable. The document provides a multitude of templates which can be freely used and combined as individual tools. This document also contains several process descriptions, that can be used in different configurations depending on the reader and his or her personal interest and needs. Do's, don'ts, lessons learned and best practices in Berlin, Milan and Amsterdam have all contributed to the content of this elaborate resource.

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Introduction

The personalisation of healthcare

The Squeeze-a-ball; a knitted anti-stress ball and pressure sensor that registers pain levels both real-time and as pain diary. The Pimp my Cane design that helps to enhance the visibility and safety of visually impaired people by means of light emitting white canes. The Stomanoir that supports ostomates in their hygiene care by providing a sanitary solution to personal inconveniences by allowing them to close off stoma-bags after use. These are some of the designs that were the result of prototyping series, held in 2018 and 2019 in Amsterdam, aimed at developing health solutions.

As these series were successful in creating solutions that strengthen personalised healthcare, such as the above, we proudly present to you this training kit. With this training kit, we share the philosophy behind the Careables platform, and help you set up your own prototyping series. Our lessons learned have been sourced from makerspaces in Milan, Amsterdam and Berlin that all hosted events with the aim of developing health solutions. Despite slight variation in target groups, timing and context, many learnings, tips and co-design methods are shared in this document.

This document will give you all you need to get started and organise a series of events in which an interdisciplinary group of people can create meaningful prototypes and products together. We have learned a lot from our earlier event series. Now we are eager to share our knowledge and to help spread the possibilities and benefits of co-designing personalised healthcare solutions. Of course, the information we provide in this document should merely be seen as guidelines, that can be used in any way you find helpful. We hope to inspire existing communities and makerspaces, but also students of medicine, paramedical professions, design & arts, biomedical engineering and fab-academy participants.

Careables: what, why, for whom

The Careables initiative facilitates co-design of open healthcare for people that face a broad range of health challenges such as physical limitations. People's needs regarding their limitations are personal, subjective and diversified. By taking a more personalised approach to healthcare solutions, we can better cater for the needs of people and develop 'closer' to that need as well. In fact, we even ask the user to personally be involved in this development, not as a subject, but as a developer. Currently such personalisation is not often provided due to

the care industries' focus on 'one size fits all' solutions. Industrial innovation budgets are often allocated to the development of solutions that serve many people, while concepts for solutions that only serve few are left disregarded because they are labeled as commercially unfeasible.

To overcome this lack of development of meaningful and more individually tailored healthcare solutions, we started the Careables platform, that has 5 different goals:

1. Build an **ecosystem** by linking existing local communities of citizens with disabilities and their families, healthcare professionals and makers. To stimulate collaboration between these separate communities in developing their own open source and license interventions.
2. Provide access to open source and digital fabrication tools enabling citizens with disabilities and healthcare professionals, in co-creation with designers and makers (DIY communities and makerspaces) to **create customised self-made solutions** to improve quality of life or services.
3. Improve the **accessibility of open source products**; co-production of products that are tailored to people with special needs or disabilities as well as healthcare professionals and bypassing the limitations of the classical industrial production.
4. **Foster the ecosystem** through open exchange of knowledge, case stories and manuals. Within the Do It Yourself (DIY) approach, local production and global knowledge sharing is key.
5. **Build guidelines** that allow anyone to replicate formats everywhere, considering the socio-technical aspects as well as relevant legal and regulatory frameworks, This helps those who are interested to deal with things such as quality standards, Intellectual Property Right implications, security, safety and privacy issues.

The long-term goal of the Careables initiative is to affiliate a community of designers, users, fablabs and maker-spaces who develop meaningful projects and replicate events and activities in various cities all around Europe or even globally.

In this document, we share a stepwise approach towards organising a series of collaborative events around healthcare innovation. The goal of the co-design sessions is that interdisciplinary teams work on designing prototypes of personalised health solutions. We share our step-by-step approach to enable others to copy and refine this format. At the same time, readers of this document can reflect on their personal role in this process. The document will definitely

provide you with some meaningful insights in strengthening or changing your personal role in the process of healthcare solution prototyping.

The training kit: how it works

In this training kit, we have collected all the practical information you need to set up an event series and guide the process in relation to the Careables platform. The focus of this specific training kit is specifically on the organisation of a prototyping series. It gives you guidelines on how to find partners to cooperate with, how to gather a diverse group of participants, how to set up the different stages of the prototyping series and document the overall process and resulting products. This information will give you the tools to create a fruitful environment in which organisations can successfully work together and that gives participants the space to develop and design solutions, based on the needs of individual patients.

This training kit is one in a range of documents that give you guidelines to organise different events related to open healthcare and the Careables project. This training kit consists of a definition of the ambition and goals. Furthermore, it describes the process, supported by formats, of participatory co-design process in open source healthcare solutions. Do's and Don'ts are included, lessons learned and best practices shared. Depending on the specific context of the target group, this kit can be adjusted. Although focused on a prototyping series, this document also offers information on necessary preparation of any healthcare event. It is openly downloadable from the Careables website.

The process in 3 phases

Ok, let's start! If you want to organise a complete co-design series - or any other public event related to Careables - quite some actions are required before and after the actual events. We therefore provide an overview of the phases you as organiser have to go through when organizing an event from start to finish. We distinguish three different phases:

- Preparing the prototyping series
- Guiding the prototyping series
- Reflecting on the prototyping series

The phases are discussed in the following chapters of this training kit. Each chapter goes through the steps that a phase consists of. It might not be necessary for you to go through every step, so feel free to only focus on the parts that you need.

The total overview of the phases regarding the prototyping series is presented below:

Organising prototype series for healthcare innovation

We hope the information will help you gather the resources you need to engage people, deliver the project, and navigate some of the common challenges you might face along the way.

Phase 1: Preparing the prototyping series

The first phase is all about getting started. This chapter takes you through all the steps of the preparation process: from finding partners and launching an open call to getting people engaged, arranging practical needs and setting up the documentation environment.

These steps can also function as reminder list. They help you to make sure that you think of everything you need to set up your prototyping series.

1. Organisation: finding partners

One of the goals of Careables is to create an ecosystem around personalised health solutions. It is therefore important that you focus on this from the start, by connecting partner organisations to your initiative that can facilitate or support it. Most importantly, it is necessary to connect the health community, such as a health organisation or hospital, to the makers community or a fablab. Both parties provide essential input for the co-design of personalised healthcare tools.

Some organisations already have a strong network with ties to makers, individuals with an interest in technology, and healthcare professionals.

However, for other organisations, such as healthcare providers, the outreach to makers might be more challenging, because they have not yet connected to the maker community before. The engagement methods below can help you to reach different audiences, including these communities.

2. Open Call: finding participants

The most important way to engage people and a key part of any prototyping series related to Careables is the organisation of an Open Call. Through an Open Call, you can invite interested care professionals, makers, and individuals facing any healthcare challenge to join and co-create meaningful health innovations. This Open Call is the launch of your series and potentially delivers the ideas that will be further developed during the co-design sessions. In other words: the Open Call is a way to actively send out an invitation for others to join. It is therefore a way of pre-scanning interest and ideas.

The best concepts that are submitted can be further developed and prototyped in the prototyping series. To ensure that outcomes of the Open Call result in ideas that are suitable for a prototyping series, it is helpful to provide some guidelines for the registrations. Guidelines should help you maintain a healthcare related focus and they should help people to be specific.

In the registration forms for participation of the event, it is good to ask people to share to which groups they most strongly relate themselves. When setting up digital participant acquisition and registration, it is therefore advisable to ask for people's background.

If your event series has an educational character you may use the approach for recruiting participants that the Open Health HACKdemy applies. This format is specifically geared towards interdisciplinary teams with students from different disciplines, people with disabilities and makers that jointly develop open-source hardware solutions, so-called Careables together. It is an educative format that gets delivered in a Fab Lab environment with three thematic co-design sprints (WE UNDERSTAND, WE MAKE, WE SHARE) in a timeframe of 10 Days.

The HACKademy organizers structured their Open Call in 2 Phases: the first phase was dedicated to finding users with a real need that could be addressed by developing a careable. This led to design briefs in which the specific case-story was shared. In the second phase a call for participants was launched to attract people with skills and interests that could play a role in defining and creating the careables based on the case-stories.

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Participants were asked to use a sign up form that was embedded on the event website. In this form participants were inquired about learning motivation, maker-skills, team types and experience regarding health topics. Asking quite detailed questions helped matching the interdisciplinary teams in advance and the planning and selection of additional resources. The Full Questionnaire can be found in the Appendix 10.

3. Engagement: creating a community

The announcement of the Open Call is a good way to inform people about your initiative. But, to make sure different communities are informed about the Open Call and that you receive ample responses, you will need to spread the word as well. This part of the chapter gives you a range of engagement strategies, that help to stimulate engagement and reach different groups of people. This might include designers, makerspaces, students of relevant studies, professionals in the care industry and possible users that potentially have questions in regards to a health challenge.

We mention these methods here so that you as reader can get a grasp of the activities that can be deployed to boost your initiative. It also gives an idea of the materials that have already been created, and that you can access and use. As each organisation of a prototyping series will be different and depends on the local context and organisational partners, it is up to the organisers to create a suitable combination of engagement methods.

A. Outreach materials: texts and tools

To spread the word about your Open Call, you will need to develop outreach materials. This includes an announcement and a description of the envisioned projects. To spread your text, think for example of using newsletters you have access to, or send personal invitations to people with a valuable network. By creating personalised texts for each of your target groups separately, you are able to address them in a direct and relevant manner. Think about translating your outreach materials into different languages to ensure the reach of an international audience.

Because you are working on an innovative project, you can also reach out to local press, that might be interested in writing about your initiative. This is a great way to reach a large, local community. One way to do so is by writing out press releases in which you introduce the project and invite journalists for the final exposition.

If you have the means to do so, it can be very productive to create a project website, where you can collect all the relevant information in one place, including important information and a contact form. This platform can also be used to inform the people that are not participants, but are interested in your project. Writing blogs or short reports about the progress of your co-design sessions, can be a good way to do so.

The Careables platform also offers the opportunity to share your event with a large community to let them know what you are planning. An alternative is to use the Meetup platform, that can help you to create a community and communicate about events. There is e.g. an existing Amsterdam based 'Make Health' community to which you can connect. In addition, communities like the Amsterdam-based 'Sensemakers' are valuable, as it includes people that are looking for challenges related to electronics and coding. Similar groups exist in most larger cities. They are nice to approach and can help you amplify your message.

If a direct network to the imagined participants is missing, we advise to look for cooperation with organisations that already have strong or strong ties to a missing target group. This is a way to compensate for missing links with makers of other relevant stakeholders that are not part of the existing network (yet).

B. Meetups, presentations and workshops

Prior to or during the Open Call, you can create physical moments where you provide people with more information. Meetups, presentations and workshops offer an opportunity to invite different organisations and people to join the conversation on open healthcare solutions. We call such events pre-events. Participants of these events can be valuable candidates for the Open Call. They can also share ideas or projects they are working on.

Interesting places to meet are local community centres, because these venues bring together citizens from the neighbourhood. These locations can be a good place to organise pre-events, but also might be a good location for the first prototyping series, in which you do not need access to a fablab yet.

You can choose to spread outreach to wider stakeholder groups by including particular legal experts, policy makers and relevant public sector stakeholders to stimulate broader discussions around critical ethical and policy relevant aspects. However, this depends on the scope of what you want to set up, and topics you aim to cover.

In order to spread wider public awareness and make use of existing communities, you can present your initiative at existing events. These events can include hosting open health specific areas at maker-related events such as Makerfaires, re:publica, the annual Fabconference or other relevant, local events.

C. Open days

Consider organising open days specifically targeted on open healthcare. These open days are aimed at starting the development of prototyping solutions with citizens or healthcare professionals, but are also aimed to inspire stakeholders and the general public. The hubs in Amsterdam, Berlin and Milan, for example hosted many Open Days throughout the initial project. This also helped to keep the community they involved intact. Open days can provide a way of pointing new participants towards your prototyping series. However, it is also likely that it will be a time and place where participants keep meeting after the prototyping series or other events.

D. Maker gatherings

Although fablabs and makerspaces have numerous platforms and networks at their disposal to collaborate, these opportunities are seldom used to their full potential. Exchange of experience on a broad - even global - scale stimulates exchange of knowledge between labs on creation of different types of solutions as well as documentation processes.

Maker gatherings focus on getting people of the maker community together. These gatherings provide ways to exchange approaches to open healthcare of non-EU labs with European labs, to further share experiences in global collaboration and to activate knowledge transfer. Besides physical attendance, online collaboration tools can be used to keep the momentum going and share best practices.

Maker gatherings could help you gather insights, network and best practices to make your prototyping series the best it can be. However, this activity is more important for organisations with a broad scope that want to set up a multi-lab prototyping series, of who aim to locally develop for a healthcare challenge in a different geographical location. It is less relevant for organisers aiming to set up a mainly local oriented event. However, we do want to emphasize that there is a lot to learn from others in the maker community that can add value to your prototyping series.

E. Education activities and student engagement

It is valuable to reach out to communities of students as a way of tapping into a broad range of knowledge and skills to be represented in your prototyping sessions. Depending on which skill you need for your series, you can involve students in fields like medicine, paramedical professions, design & arts, biomedical engineering and fabacademy. Being part of a prototyping series can be a valuable learning experience for these students. They can be involved in the process of co-design and delivery of people-centered healthcare solutions and they will learn how to be involved in this participatory co-design process within their expertise. Their expertise will surely add value to your prototyping series. It's a win-win situation. However, be sure to support the students because working in these settings has quite often shown to be new to them.

F. Engagement with existing open healthcare communities

For the initial Careables project, a first inventory of worldwide organisations and communities that are active in open healthcare has been developed. Organisational partners can reach out to these communities to connect and share insights on their work. All communities that have been inspired and connected by the Careables initiative will be visualised on a community map. The map will be provided on the Careables platform.

G. Other setup documents to inspire you

More background information on the Careables initiative can be found online on www.carebles.com. Besides this document, information on other events and how to set them up is provided there. You can set up an event as a one-time happening, but also feel free to organise them strongly connected to closely related prototyping series.

4. Preparations: the prototyping sessions

Ok, so now that we have shared our advice on spreading the word about other events and communities that can be related to your prototyping series, it is time to involve your participants and set up the actual prototyping series. Before you can start taking people through the actual co-design steps, these are the important things you need to take care of:

- Invite participants
- Manage participant expectations
- Assign a sessions coordinator
- Take care of practical necessities
- Structure the co-design process

A. Invite participants

Let's assume you now have asked makers, healthcare professionals and individuals with healthcare challenges to respond to your Open Call to join the prototyping series. Then, it is time to go through the submissions and select participants. These participants will be asked to collaborate in interdisciplinary teams and further work on ideas.

Go through the registrations and assess whether there is a balance between individuals that propose challenges to work on, makers or designers to help in prototyping different solutions and healthcare professionals to support the development process from a medical perspective. If, during the preparation and registration period, you see that these groups are not balanced, some more targeted acquisition can take place in preparation of the event.

When the subscriptions are collected, you can see whether it is necessary to make a sub-selection of participants. Another option is to invite everyone, and use the first co-design session as an occasion for pitching project ideas. Afterwards, you can monitor the composition of team formations in co-design session one. It is recommended to set up a maximum number of participants for the registration process, in relation to the capacity of your prototyping series. We have had four as an average group size. Limit yourself to how many of those groups you think you can monitor and guide with your team.

Try to make sure that users themselves are part of the group of participants, as they are the end users that products will be designed for and because they can express the need for health products based on their own experiences. If the health challenge at hand permits it, we always prioritise prototyping with people, not for people.

B. Manage participant expectations

In communication about the co-design process it is important to provide clarity about the setup of the programme. Emphasise that it is not an event where people pitch ideas that afterwards will be produced by a team of professionals. Instead, it is an event in which participants are asked to contribute to the development of products themselves, in collaboration with a varied team of individuals. Participants have to be willing to invest time in the development of the designs. This is essential information to align the expectations of potential participants with the actual setup of the programme.

C. Assign a co-design session coordinator and other roles

An important role to assign is that of co-design session coordinator. As coordinator, it is your role to make sure there is a productive and inclusive worksphere, and that the participants feel guided through the steps of the co-design process. As every step in the process has a different goal, the role of co-design session coordinator will vary throughout the process. The coordinator has to be present during all the co-design sessions and makes sure that participants stay on track. In Appendix one, we also share info on determining other important roles such as Team-Coach, Prototyping Expert, Evaluator or Participant. This is based on best practices in Berlin and is meant to help you to clarify and facilitate cooperation between a bigger Team including Participants.

D. Take care of practical necessities

Hosting a series of events also requires to take care of some practical things. Here is a list:

- choose an accessible location for the meetings in your prototyping series
- arrange accessibility of a fablab (not needed in the first two co-design sessions)
- arrange food and drinks
- arrange (prototyping) materials and worksheets to work with
- arrange visual documentation (photographer)

E. Structure the co-design process

The co-design process is divided into six steps, which can be covered in co-design sessions in anyway that fit with your ideas and the available time. This could mean that the six steps are all separate co-design sessions, are spread out over more sessions, or that each session goes through multiple steps. Create a feasible schedule that fits your needs and share this with the participants.

If the series ends with a public exhibition, choose a suitable place and time, prepare to send out an invitation to the community and make sure you have some refreshments for the group.

5. Documentation: two types explained

An important part of the co-design process is to document the different steps teams go through. Documentation is an essential way to share the insights gathered during the co-design process with each other and the wider community.

We recommend to distinguish between two types of documentation:

1. Progress document: a reflection on the co-design process; the different design steps, the progress being made and the lessons learned. This kind of documentation resembles a captains-log.
2. Instruction document: an explanation of how the final product can be made, what is needed and how it works. This kind of documentation resembles a recipe.

With each step of the co-design process, the instructions include an indication of what kind of documentation is asked from the participants and the co-design session coordinator. Welder.app is an example of a platform that should be used for documentation and that was developed within the Careables project. Welder caters for both progress documents and instruction documents. How that works is explained here.

The reason for separation of the documentation in two documents is to cater for the need of the individuals that want to read about the project. These people will have different interests. By providing instructions and progress reporting in separate places, makers are not confronted with endless stories about failed material that they are not interested in. At the same time people who want to understand the project-related learning process might be unsatisfied when only part-lists and practicalities are presented.

Progress document

The progress document is about the design research and about the process (what you try, how you fail). The best way of setting up such a document on Welder is through completing the basic information of the overview page first, and then adding a separate editable text file to log your progress every time you work on your project. Every time teams actually create a new project prototype, it is helpful to refer to a separate individual instruction document each time, in which the creation of the prototype itself is described.

Instruction document

The instruction document gives an instruction of how to make a (final) version of the project. When creating several final versions of a project, it is advised not to replace old versions of this file with an improved one, but to include and keep previous file versions. Doing so creates an overview of project versions. Do not include all your research in the instruction document. It is better to describe that in the progress document. The best way of adding an instruction document on Welder is through adding a so called "assembly guide". In this document you can provide a stepwise description on how your prototype is made.

As a starting point for these documents, we provided two templates in the appendix (7 and 8) that contain a structure with relevant subjects that could be a part of the description. Again, these structures should be seen as suggestions.

Besides the written documentation, it is very valuable if participants take photos and videos during the process. As a co-design session coordinator, it is important to stimulate participants to make time for documentation, as experience has shown participants are mostly focussed on the prototyping itself, and do not always see the value of documentation. It is however an important way to share the knowledge they have gathered during the co-design sessions with the wider personalised health community. By making time for documentation in every session, you can stimulate that the teams remain up to date. Be sure to make documentation an integral part of your prototyping series.

Phase 2: Guiding the prototyping series

Ok. So now you are all set up to actually start the series. This chapter provides an overview of the actual hands on co-design process that we advise participants to go through, guided by a co-design session coordinator. The visual on the right hand side illustrates the 6 steps that this process consists of:

As mentioned before, it is up to you to structure these steps as you wish. They are designed as six different co-design sessions of 4 hours each, but this can be adjusted. Keep in mind that if you shorten the sessions, the participants might have less developed prototypes as end products.

Each step is explained in a similar way. It starts with basic information about the goal of the session, the role of the coordinator and the materials that are needed. Then it takes you through the setup of the co-design session. Worksheets and assignments that you can use in these sessions can be found in the appendices.

If you are looking for an alternative you should check the The Manifesto of Co-design, which suggests a slightly different stepwise approach. It also highlights some meaningful points of attention within the process. Be sure to check that out in Appendix 9.

Phase

2

Stages of the design process

Welcome: introductions and getting started

Research: the challenge, users and solutions

Concept development: working on a solution

Prototyping I: prototyping and presenting ideas

Prototyping II: prototyping and documenting

1. Welcome: introductions and getting started

Goal of the session

Step 1 is primarily about introduction, setting the scene and creating an open and comfortable atmosphere. The groups will be formed and will make a first start with their co-design concept.

Role of the coordinator

Make participants feel welcome, and feel safe to talk about sensitive issues that will come up during this co-design session. Introduce the overall programme, so that participants know what to expect.

Structure of the session

1. Introduce co-design session coordinator
2. Introductory assignment
3. Introduce Careables
4. Pitching ideas
5. Forming groups
6. Create outline for concept development
7. Documentation

What you need

- printed out assignment forms
- brainstorm materials: post-its, papers, markers, scissors, tape

Documentation goals

Set up the documentation environment and write a reflection on this co-design session.

1. Introduce co-design session coordinator

Introduce (yourself as) the co-design session coordinator and explain the basics of the overall co-design process and this session more specifically. Take time to note who of the registered participants is actually present, and whether there are people that did not sign up previously. Make sure to thank everyone for coming and for their willingness to invest time in this intensive project.

2. Introduction of participants

Take some time for introductions, so that the participants get to know each other. To set the scene and create a productive and open setting, it can be helpful to use a playful exercise, see assignment 1 in appendix 1. The goal of this is that people get to know each other, and that they feel comfortable enough to discuss personalised health topics.

3. Introduce Careables and the co-design session

Give a brief introduction of the Careables platform and programme, so that participants are reminded of the goals of the programme, know the practicalities, and are given some inspiration for their own co-design process. Think for example of:

- Using the Positive Health definition as a starting point of being able to influence health yourself. This definition emphasises that health is about succeeding in facing diverse personal challenges. Not merely about being free of injuries or illness;
- Elaborating on different reasons why people decide to make their own solutions;
- Showing inspiring examples;
- Presenting the setup of the entire series, including the exhibition that the series will end with;
- Stressing the relevance of documentation;
- Talking about licensing the product ideas;
- Providing clarity on available budgets if relevant.

4. Pitching ideas

After a brief presentation of the Careables platform and the concept of the design sessions, the next step will be idea pitching. The idea pitching should not be set up as a competition but as friendly sharing, in which participants feel comfortable to share their experiences.

5. Forming groups

After all project ideas are shared, teams are formed by asking people to join the project that they are (most) interested in. Any project that is related to healthcare is eligible, but the preference of participants determines which of the pitches will be further developed. Session coordinators play an important guiding role in this process, that has to be handled with sensitivity and care. As coordinator, it is important you make sure that:

- you monitor group size (ideally 3-5 people) and spread of skills across different teams.
- people are motivated to work on the project of their group. It is therefore of great importance that people are allowed to work on projects that they themselves feel passionate about.
- every group ideally has one - possibly imagined - end user, that can represent the user perspective within the group. However, the best thing is to have the actual user on board.

Some ideas will not be further developed, either because they are too complicated and developing a prototype in the limited time is not feasible, or because there are no, or not enough, participants that choose the project. This can be a disappointing moments for the participants that pitched these ideas. Make sure that you talk to each participant in this situation, take them serious and help them to think of alternatives. Maybe a project can be developed in a slightly altered way or the participant is willing to work on another project. Try to be as supportive as possible.

6. Create outline for concept development

When groups are formed, the groups can start an initial brainstorm. For that co-design session, you can provide groups with a bit of an outline based on a few questions they can ask themselves. Use assignment 2 for this, see appendix 2.

7. Documentation

Reserve some time for the groups to set up their documentation.

2. Research: the challenge, users and solutions

● ● ● Goal of the session

Step 2 is primarily about developing the initial ideas by further researching the problem and starting early concept creation. Teams will also research possible solutions, and aim to come up with one solution they want to work on in following co-design sessions.

● ● ● Role of the coordinator

Make sure teams identify the most important aspects of the challenge, integrate the end user, and the possible solutions they could work on.

● ● ● Structure of the session

1. Explore the challenge
2. Create persona of the end user
3. Create a design brief
4. Map out possible solutions
5. Documentation

● ● ● What you need

- the assignment forms printed
- brainstorm materials: post-its, papers, markers, scissors, tape

● ● ● Documentation goals

Document the challenge and solution and write a reflection on this design session.

1. Explore the challenge

First, further explore the challenges that have been discussed in step 1. Make sure teams identify the most important aspects of the challenge they choose to work on, and that they keep the end user close in mind. This will guide them through the design process and production of your prototype. Teams can ask themselves a range of questions, See appendix 3.

2. Create persona of the end user

The next step is to zoom in on the end user. Create a persona of the end user by using the sheet, See appendix 4. In many cases, this user will (hopefully) be a part of the team. Using the overview of assignment 3, people can have a guideline for a conversation with this user in order to get a better understanding of the person that teams are developing for. If there are multiple user groups, this exercise can be repeated. If teams do not value this structure, they are free to empathise in ways that seem better suited to them.

3. Create a design brief

For the following steps 3 & 4, there is another tool that the groups can use. This is a design brief (Appendix 5) that gives the group a tool to make an overview of the challenge they want to work on, the end user and the solution they will focus on. See Appendix 5. This format can be filled with post-its in a brainstorm session. It helps teams to go from a central challenge or issue to relevant directions for further development, without ignoring what already exists.

The design brief can help the groups with collecting their insights and specifying the direction they want to take as a group.

4. Map out possible solutions

The rest of the design brief focuses on solutions.

- Brainstorm on possible solutions. Appendix 5 will help you make a start in this, and appendix 6 can support a further brainstorm about this. Brainstorming on solutions can also mean that you think of possible modifications of existing solution. Don't limit yourselves to one idea, but try to come up with several solutions.
- Choose the solution that you will be working on. Start sketching and designing, if you have time.

5. Documentation

Let the groups document the concept they have developed so far, and write a short reflection on the co-design session.

3. Concept development: working on a solution

● ● ● Goal of the session

Step 3 is devoted to the development of the concept that groups chose to work on in the prior step. They are also invited to start prototyping using the means at hand.

● ● ● Structure of the session

1. Discuss progress
2. Start prototyping
3. Documentation

● ● ● Role of the coordinator

Consult with the different teams to make sure they have what they need to realise their projects. Emphasise the importance of prototyping as a step to further developing the concept.

● ● ● What you need

brainstorm materials: post-its, papers, markers, scissors, tape materials for prototyping

● ● ● Documentation goals

Document the progress and initial prototype ideas and write a reflection on this session.

1. Discuss progress

As a co-design session coordinator you are advised to consult with the different teams in this session, so that they all stay on track and move from concepting to prototyping. Based on their further directions, the co-design session coordinator can assist by connecting the team with other individuals that have the necessary skills to materialise the proposed concept directions.

2. Start prototyping

The coordinator is supposed to facilitate in concept creation, but also to convince the teams that prototyping is a necessary next step. Teams tend to conceptualise until they have discovered the perfect solution, which may get them stuck. Instead, rapid prototyping is an important step to proceed to in an early stage because the teams will learn a lot just by developing and testing their initial ideas. Teams learn a lot by doing, for example about the needed materials for the realisation of their concept. Before teams are willing to move on to prototyping, it is often important to start from a shared perception that all prototyping adds knowledge and that there is no such thing as failure.

3. Documentation

In this third design session, coordinators should also further elaborate on the topic of documentation. Now that teams start prototyping, it is relevant to discuss the two different types of documentation, and advise the teams to document every prototyping concept.

4. Prototyping I: prototyping and presenting ideas

● ● ● Goal of the session

Step 4 is about prototyping and sharing experiences.

● ● ● Role of the coordinator

Make sure teams do not get stuck with prototyping, and create an environment in which teams can learn from each other.

● ● ● Structure of the session

1. Prototyping
2. Presentations
3. Documentation

● ● ● What you need

prototyping materials depending on project needs

● ● ● Documentation goals

Document the progress and developments in prototyping and write a reflection on this co-design session.

1. Prototyping

This co-design session is dedicated to prototyping. Session coordinators can assist the teams by being sensitive to the prototyping needs in the different projects. The best way to do this is by going around and asking how things are progressing. Progress will differentiate among groups: some might come up with a physical object soon, while others remain doubtful about their concept. As a session coordinator, you might not be able to change the dynamics of the group, but you can support groups by listening, suggesting ideas or encouraging them to start building.

2. Presentations

By making time for short presentations, teams can present their initial prototypes to each other and share their knowledge or questions. However, experience has shown that teams value having a lot of time to work on prototyping. It is therefore advised that you limit the length of presentations to a minimum, and that if you choose to do presentations the setup is adjusted to the needs of participants at that specific time in the process.

Presentation can be limited to 3 min. presentation + 2min. feedback time. Even though this might seem very short to some, it is surprising how effectively information can be condensed into the main aspects in a short timeframe.

You may also run a testing roulette exercise where teams would test each others Ideas and give feedback in a scenario testing style and not frontal presentation. Each team sends 1-2 team members to the neighbouring team on their right while 1-2 team members come from the team on their left. The team members that stay at their teamspace/workplace do the testing and document the insights they gain from it in a feedback grid and share them with their team members that went for testing (s. Appendix 11.2). After a short phase of iteration you can run another round and switch roles within the team for a different learning perspective.

3. Documentation

Give the teams some time to document their prototyping concepts and reflect on the co-design process.

5. Prototyping II: prototyping and documenting

● ● ● Goal of the session

This co-design session also revolves around prototype development and finishing the prototypes. It is also the moment to work on project documentation.

● ● ● Role of the coordinator

Make sure teams finalise their prototypes and are on track with documentation.

● ● ● Structure of the session

1. Prototyping
2. Documentation

● ● ● What you need

- prototyping materials

● ● ● Documentation goals

Document the precise steps for the design of the prototype and write a reflection on this co-design session.

1. Prototyping

This is the last session for teams that is dedicated to prototyping. As a session coordinator, make sure you assist the teams wherever you can. Motivate groups that have not started prototyping, to create an actual object. It does not have to be perfect, but it helps groups to see their progress so far and realise what else they need to do.

2. Documentation

Monitor if people are finding their way in the documentation process, and motivate them to make sure their documentation is complete. Inform if they have any suggestions for improving the online infrastructure for project documentation. This could also be a suitable moment to ask how they have experienced the co-design process, and whether they have suggestions on how to improve it.

6. Exposition: presenting the final products

● ● ● Goal of the session

This co-design session is devoted to finalising the prototypes and preparing them for presentations to an audience.

● ● ● Role of the coordinator

Make sure teams feel good with the result that they have achieved and are proud to share their status quo. Support their final decisions and help them to communicate their results clearly.

● ● ● Structure of the session

1. Finish prototyping
2. Preparing for exposition
3. Exposition

● ● ● What you need

- prototyping materials
- paper sheets
- presentation materials

● ● ● Documentation goals

Document the chosen challenge and solution and reflect on the entire co-design process.

1. Finish prototyping

In this last co-design session, allow for some final prototyping. Some groups will really need some more time to work on their prototypes. Make sure that they can still use the facilities of a makerspace, and that you as session coordinator are available to help. Make sure that groups also finish their documentation.

2. Preparing for exposition

Provide the teams with paper sheets or other means, so that they can prepare the presentation of their products to the audience.

3. Exposition

At a clearly communicated time in the co-design sessions, doors are opened to the general public that is invited beforehand. Of course this general public includes friends and family of participants. As a session coordinator, you can give a brief introduction (presentation) of the Careables platform, and why this sessions took place. It might be nice to invite guest speakers that can give a short presentation on the topic of open health.

Afterwards, the entire group passes by the tables of participants. At each table, the session coordinator interviews one spokesperson per project. Every project gets an even amount of attention. Please provide amplification if needed. This need depends on space and amount of people.

Lastly, visitors are offered a drink, and the opportunity to revisit different projects that have been developed. Teams themselves can answer any further questions.

Phase 3: Reflecting on the prototyping series

1. Reflection: evaluating the prototyping series

Looking back on the process is a valuable exercise. If you are planning more activities in the future, it is important to think back on what worked well and what could be improved: you might consider how you would approach interested parties differently, or how you might use a different setup of the prototyping series. It is also important to think about whether the community will want to continue working together after the end of the process, and how you might continue to assist in this open health research.

The community and yourself as a hosting organisation(s) should take the opportunity to think back on the whole process to date. At this stage, you may want to collaborate on making changes to the setup of the prototyping series. You may also wish to consider collecting data to determine how the community's knowledge and feelings have developed during the prototyping series. With this information in mind, you might begin scoping and planning a new prototyping series.

One way to reflect on the series is by sending around a questionnaire to participants. Questionnaires encourage community members to document their experiences and ideas about the problem. In turn, their feedback can help you reflect on the campaign thus far, and gain insight for future iterations and activities. Such reflection does not have to limit itself to the end of the entire series. It can also be planned in as part of the individual meetings (as part of

a wrapup) in which opinions can be openly discussed in group talks. These opinions can also be further analysed in interviews with individual participants.

2. Sharing lessons: how to continue

Besides taking time for reflection, it is valuable to spread the knowledge that you as organiser, or the participants, gained during the prototyping series. Ideally, the overarching legacy from the work conducted would be a measurable change, such as new health products or new partnerships between institutions. Your project might even lead to local council policy changes.

Think about how you can communicate the results of your Careables project with a wider community, for example through the Careables platform, or other engagement tools that you have used earlier in the process. You might also think about publishing some of your work formally, or sharing it in reports or newspaper articles. Another way to further spread the word about open health and the Careables initiative, is to ask makers or users that have been related to your project to be ambassador. People that are excited about the initiative and can inform others about it, make great ambassadors.

On a long-term basis, it is important to connect the people that have contributed to your initiative over time with each other. Think of how you can support prototypes that will be further developed, and how you can give these developments a platform too. If you are organising multiple series, it is nice to keep supporting projects from prior design sessions, or introducing them in new series.

Final general advise

That was a lot to take in already. However, in this chapter we still want to present some last pointers and talk about other formats for similar innovation series. We will also share pointwise preconditions and lessons learned for hosting a successful healthcare prototyping series.

Different formats for a similar process

The process that has been described above is based on the basic principles of the co-design process. According to local contexts, the target groups you want to reach and the results you want to achieve it can be remixed, adjusted and used in very different ways.

In careables we also worked with educational formats and structured the

process in formats that were inspired by summer schools. One such approach was the “Open Health HACKademy”. It is an educative format hosted in a Fab Lab Environment that caters to students from various disciplines and is also open to professionals. It is delivered in three design sprints (WE UNDERSTAND, WE MAKE, WE SHARE) in a timeframe of 10 days. The development teams that consist of a case-provider (a user with a real user need) and people with skills, dedication and timely resources to solve that case together, are accompanied and supported by experienced coaches from the fields of electronic prototyping, coding, digital fabrication and design thinking. A program with process supporting inputs on prototyping techniques, the design process, how to open source hardware, documentation for open source hardware, storytelling and public presentations frames and supports the practical work of the development teams. (You can find descriptions of roles in Appendix 1 and templates for teamwork and user centered co-design that were used and partly developed in this program in Appendix 11/12).

Likewise, the “Health & Care Summer School” generated useful templates. These are shared in Appendix 13.

Do's and Don'ts

Session coordinator

Include one or more coordinators per co-design session. Be really clear about who the general spokesperson is, so no confusion arises. The session coordinator has an important task in motivating participants, catering for their needs and monitoring the progress of each group.

Give participants freedom

During the sessions, people are free to plan work themselves. Allow for ambition and time investment to be determined by teams themselves. Consider allowing the teams to gather at different location to process work in an extracurricular setting. If that is possible, it is often greatly appreciated and it can provide an additional boost of progress.

Create a safe environment

As the co-design series touches upon sensitive and personal health issues, it is important to ensure a safe environment for participants. They have to feel comfortable to share their experiences with the group and feel motivated to work on their project.

Provide food and drinks

Providing food and drinks during the co-design session really helps people to keep energy levels high when working together. Furthermore eating together also strengthens the social bond within teams and among the entire group.

Provide name tags

Based on the first introduction, coordinators can develop nametags which might also give some insight in skillsets of the different participants.

Organise presentation moments

Session coordinators can choose when they have groups reporting on their projects. Either after different exercises, or at the end of sessions. In wrap up sessions, the different teams are asked to report on progress, and to ask questions to the entire group of participants. This is a way of crowdsourcing solutions for challenges that the individual teams face.

All tools are optional

None of the tools we offer are obligatory. Our experience has shown that people perform best if they themselves remain responsible and respected managing their own progress in ways they themselves see fit.

Be clear about budgets and declarations

Give the participants clear instructions if they are given the option for reimbursement for certain costs or not. If that is the case, it helps when participants are provided with a form to submit receipts of costs they are allowed to make for the project. These forms are set up in such a way that they are processable by the financial administration of the hosting organisation. Be as clear as possible, not only about budget, but also about the VAT situation when explaining this process to the participants.

Think about language

Keep vocabulary non-specific to keep the co-design sessions as accessible as possible. Talking about Lean Six Sigma or Theory of Constraints may make the event more "corporate" than it needs to be, While only emphasizing sketches and git version tracking might make it too "techy". These things like vocabulary and tone of voice are important when trying to present something to appeal to a wide range of participants.

Licensing

Bring up licensing early on in the project. We only brought this up at the end of the first open Call. Participants replied to that by saying that licensing should have been something they discussed in the first session already. In the second

and third series of the OpenCall we indeed included the subject of licensing in the earlier sessions

Be strict with timing

Do allow for inspirational speakers to clarify some themes during the OpenCall co-design sessions. However, also guard the fact that the teams need 90% of the time in the series for hands on project development and prototyping.

Think about accessibility

Mind the accessibility of the venue. To make the event as inclusive as possible, it is preferred to find an event location/makerspace that provides wheelchair access (and check for accessibility of lavatory facilities as well). Be aware that noise levels, good lighting, presentation slide decks with high contrast and bold letters can be important aspects for accessibility too. You might want to consider having a sign language interpreter for people from deaf communities. Always communicate the accessibility of your venue in your invitations.

Use templates to guide thoughts and actions in the right direction.

Templates really help in taking people through the prototyping process. In addition to the templates provided already, we therefore advise you to also take a look at Appendix 13. This document provides templates that serve various purposes to guide the co-design process, from the brainstorming of ideas to the carrying out of the final prototype. In detail in focusses of:

- how to define the concept in the best way in relation to the need
- how to create a positive dialogue with the people they are designing for
- how to navigate between CNC machines, technologies and the world of sensors and actuators
- how to efficiently organize the workflow
- how to best communicate the project
- how to document the process and the final project to make it comprehensible, shared online and replicable by all.

APPENDIX 1 // Role clarification (advanced)

The Berlin case: Assigning clear Roles to every person involved

We have learnt in past programmes that a clear distribution and communication of roles within the organizing Team as also towards the outside is essential. The more complex and diverse your program, the more important it becomes that everyone knows what are their main tasks and obligations and where they can find answers, advise and help with different questions that might occur throughout the process. Furthermore we experienced it as a good tool for expectation management.

In the following we will describe the main Roles that we defined for the Open Health HACKademy:

Coordinator, Team Coach, Prototyping Expert, Mentor, Case Provider, Participant, Documentor, Evaluator, External Communicator

Coordinator

Quote: "I keep the overview of all tasks, processes and people"

Keywords: The bridge to all stakeholders, an ear for everyone, balance

Biggest Motivation: Shaping a process where people strive and grow and real projects come to live.

Biggest Challenge: Juggling all the needs of a bunch of diverse people (external and internal)

Main Tasks:

- Co-Designing, moderating and adjusting the over all process
- Delegating tasks well so everything runs smoothly
- Give orientation and guidance for everyone
- Organizing Team Meetings

Team Coach

Quote: "I support my team in it's teamprocess"

Keywords: link between team and coordinator, guidance, orientation, seeing the meta level, stability and safety

Biggest Motivation: Support humans to reach their learning and project goals.

Biggest Challenge: Not becoming a team member.

Main Tasks:

- Enabling self organisation
- Guiding the teams process continuously

- Providing structure where needed
- Kickstarting and supporting team building
- Moderating in conflict
-

Prototyping Expert

Quote: "I support the HACKademy Teams with hands on".

Keywords: Flexible, on Demand,

Biggest Motivation: Invest the own competencies in meaningful projects to make them work.

Biggest Challenge: See where I am needed and how far my support can go

Main Tasks:

- Share basic skills through teaching them
- Give technical advice
- Provide Hands on Prototyping support

Mentor

Quote: "I contribute with challenging and motivating the teams, because I see the bigger potentials behind their Ideas!"

Keywords: Challenge, disrupt, inspire, providing the bigger picture, short interventions

Biggest Motivation: Contributing to a experimental innovative project that is deeply connected with their work.

Biggest Challenge: Understanding how to support the participants and organizers while having limited time and seeing just puzzle pieces of the process

Main Tasks:

- React in an open and respectful way to the teams ideas
- Challenge without overwhelming
- Supporting visions for coming steps
- Motivating

Case Provider

Quote: "We are a team to solve my real need for a careable."

Keywords: Dedicated, expert for his life and needs, available and open for experimentation

Biggest Motivation: To solve my own Problems with a great team that has the skills to do so!

Biggest Challenge: Being patient and grateful for whichever solution is the achievement of the Team

5 Main Tasks: Be there as an equal team member

- communicate the need,
- co-create,

- test & give feedback,
- Motivate!

Participant

Quote: "I want to have an Impact while I refine my skills!"

Keywords: Maker, Healthexpert, Projectmanager,...?

Biggest Motivation: A meaningful learning experience

Biggest Challenge: varies a lot ;)

Main Tasks:

- Being an active part of the project team bringing in their skills
- Co-create
- Being an active part of the bigger HACKademy team - support the logistics
- Being committed and responsible for the whole process (from understanding to documentation and sharing) as part of the team

Documentor

Quote: "I show the process and the emotions to help communicating what the HACKademy means for individuals."

Keywords: The ever open eye and ear, good eye, the almost invisible

Biggest Motivation: What is not documented is hard to be told!

Biggest Challenge: Be there and capture the most important moments

Main Tasks:

- Collect impressions with a good sense for aesthetics and content
- Feel and preselect what is important
- Making content available - Filling the Archive with an accessible structure

Evaluator

Quote: "Feedback is gold! I want us to learn and improve"

Keywords: Sustainability, learning for the future

Biggest Motivation: Transfer data into knowledge

Biggest Challenge: Stay neutral, don't influence

Main Tasks:

- Collect and transfer data into knowledge
- Find solid arguments for proof of concept
- Detect strength and weaknesses
- Finding opportunities for improvement

External Communicator

Quote: "Let's bring this to the world"

Keywords: social media, the voice, storytelling

Biggest Motivation: Telling meaningful stories

Biggest Challenge: reaching the right people

Main Tasks:

- Building following and adjusting a communication strategy
- Communicate, communicate, communicate
- Telling good stories
- Creating Materials for online and offline visibility

APPENDIX 2 // Assignment 1

Concept for drawing introduction:

- Form groups of two and draw your conversation partner while talking and getting to know each other
- You are NOT allowed to lift the pen from the paper
- Look at each other - so you are not looking at your paper
- Draw for 1 minute - then switch conversation partners. Collect the drawing made of you right after the conversation.
- Continue this process until people have collected 2 or 3 portraits.
- Get together with entire group. Everyone chooses 1 portrait, that you they have the strongest association with. Everyone in the group presents reason why they like it: I.e. it resembles my creativity / I like the cubist style / the drawing matches my out-of-the-box thinking.

This exercise will result many funny drawings, and will help in setting a comfortable scene for later co-creation. Coordinators only need paper, pens and possible some rigid (cardboard) background which they can use to draw while standing up. Only choose this approach if participants are physically able to join.

APPENDIX 3 // Assignment 2

Outline for concept development

You will start exploring the challenge by generating ideas or solutions.

The aim is to think freely, be associative. Nothing is crazy, you can think and dream up anything you'd want. Let your inspiration flow. Go nuts! An idea doesn't have to be practical or feasible. You'll have the opportunity to judge the ideas for their impact, desirability or their feasibility at a later stage.

- Formulate ideas or solutions for the challenge. Write down your associations (key words). Draw your solutions or ideas. Don't limit yourself to the challenge, but be creative and exchange with your team members.
- Create a list of minimum 10 ideas. Make sure that you don't list variations to one idea.
- Create a top 5 ideas with your team. Discuss why you chose a specific idea.

(Feel free to also, fold, tear, cut, stick or do whatever helps the flow of ideas.)

APPENDIX 4 // Assignment 3

Step 1

- Describe the challenge: what is it that needs to be solved?
- Describe the challenge in indicators?
 - A What are the limitations?
 - B What does this mean?
 - C How does this manifest in real life?
- Research current state:
 - A Are there existing solutions?
 - B Are these sufficient?
 - C Do they fit the needs? Why so or why not?
- Is there (academic) research available? What are the insights?
- First, map out your subject:
 - A Include existing solutions, if there are any.
 - B Check the needs of end user (persona).

User

Describe the end user or target group, use the format of persona.

- What are characteristics of this person?
- What are ambitions of this person?
- How is a day in the life of this person?

APPENDIX 5 // Design Brief

This document describes a brief overview of your project. It includes the characteristics of the end user, key objectives and scope. These are the requirements to keep in mind during the development and prototyping process.

Project:

User:

Brief Prepared by:

Date:

Review/updates:

Challenge: Use this section to describe the challenge that you want to solve or improve. State the relevance, necessity or need from the perspective of the end user.

End user / user group: Give a detailed description of the end user. Include details as gender, age, ambitions, needs, lifestyle preferences, daily activities etc. You can also refer to the persona (if you've developed this).

Insight: Share your most relevant insight based on your research of existing solutions, interviews or co-creation with end-users etc.

Key objectives: Explain the conclusion you've come to, based on the insight of your initial research. Include the preferences of end user, and the absolute 'no-go' for end user.

Concept / solution: Articulate the concept by revealing your initial idea or solution in a few sentences.

Scope: Detailed list of everything your solution is expected to deliver.

Not in scope: Use this section to specify design elements or functionalities that are out of scope.

Benefit: Describe the reason what the added value or impact for the end user is.

Regulatory issues: Note any regulations which will impact the design e.g. product labelling laws or healthcare regulations.

Measures of success: Describe the success factors that your solution needs to meet. How will you ensure the solution is appropriate for your end user? What activities will you conduct to ensure this?

APPENDIX 6 // Concept development tool

(this overview can be printed on an A3/A2 size paper)

APPENDIX 7 // Progress document template

Documentation // Project Title

Introduction

Proper documentation is an often forgotten, but crucial part of the design process. People need to know the steps you have taken in order to get involved. Whether it is for a potential contributor, user, or just an interested reader, any relevant steps you have taken can be paramount to their understanding of your product.

Imagine someone whom you've never met before. What would that person need to know before being able to get involved? This step by step guide will help you answer that question.

License

From the moment your project is created, it is protected under the copyright law. This means that no one can use it without your permission.

If you want to allow others to copy, distribute, and make some uses of your work while getting the credit for the work you put in it please specify a Creative Commons license that works the best for you, or any other license that might better suit your needs.

Product Category

As a general framework for specifying the life areas that your solution relates to, we embrace the categories as presented on [welder.app](#)

- LEARNING/COMMUNICATION
- MOBILITY
- OUTDOOR INSTALLATIONS
- INDOOR INSTALLATIONS
- SELF CARE
- THERAPY
- DAILY LIVING
- CAREWARE
- FUN/LEISURE

In which area does your solution enable activity or participation for people with restrictions?

Useful definitions: Activity is the execution of a task or action by an individual. Participation is involvement in a life situation. Activity limitations are difficulties an individual may have in executing activities. Participation restrictions are problems an individual may have in involvement in life situations.

The project in one sentence

Please specify what your product is and what it does. This information can be used as short introduction to your project.

What is it?

Provide a longer description of your product and what it is or does. This information can be used as a longer introduction for people that have been hooked by the photo or description of your project.

Why did you make it?

Here you can specify the reason the project started and exists. The more the project is related to the need or challenge of a problem owner or healthcare professional, the higher the chances of it being or becoming a relevant solution.

What does it do?

This space can be used to further specify what your product really does. Feel free to go into technical details.

â€‹

Research

In this section, you describe how you worked towards the final product. What steps did you take in researching and developing it. The descriptions of all your brilliant failures and key decisions will emphasise the quality of your work. It will also make it easier for others to understand your product.

Step 1:

Describe your first step here: Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat.

Step 2:

Describe your second step here: Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat.

Step 3:

Describe your third step here: Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat.

Credits and contacts

Who has been working on this? What are their expertises and (how) can they be contacted?

Use the overview above if you can not use Welder. However, we always advise groups to add their documentation directly into the Welder platform if possible. In this case, we specifically advise people to create a text file and keep the progress document updated in there,

APPENDIX 8 // Instruction document template

Instructions // Project Title

In this section you will make a description of how your project can be made. This includes all things from material list, to settings of the machine you use.

License

From the moment your project is created, it is protected under the copyright law. This means that no one can use it without your permission.

If you want to allow others to copy, distribute, and make some uses of your work while getting the credit for the work you put in it please specify a Creative Common license that works the best for you, or any other license that might better suit your needs.

Difficulty level

Is your product hard to make? Please specify whether you believe it takes a lot of experience and skill to create your product, or that it doesn't.

Tools Needed

Please specify which tools one needs to make your product

Material list

Please specify what material one needs to make this product. If you have some suggestions for (online) shops to buy this stuff, then please provide links

Time:

How much time does it take to make this?

Cost:

How much money does it cost to make this?

Sales:

Do you aim to sell this version of your prototype? If so, how can people order and what is the price for selling it?

Instruction // How can the final object be made?

Step 1:

Describe your first step here:

Step 2:

Describe your second step here:

Step 3:

Describe your third step here:

Use the overview above if you can not use Welder. However, we always advice groups to add their documentation directly into the Welder platform if possible. In this case, we specifically advise people to use the 'assembly guide'

APPENDIX 9 // OpenDOT Manifesto for HealthCare Codesign

Method developed by OpenDot from 2015 with the TOG Foundation and other organizations, ranging from patient associations to companies operating in the field of healthcare.

MANIFESTO OF CO-DESIGN FOR HEALTH AND CARE

We are all different,
then why care for
everyone the same?

Nowadays, care and health have technology and methodologies at their disposal that could definitely transform them, bettering the quality of life of millions living with disabilities, both physical and cognitive, whether temporary or permanent.

They are new tools that allow to adapt, personalize and even create more effective solutions from scratch. We are one step away from being able to take care of each other, as people, with unique tastes and necessities, not only as patients of a certain pathology.

In order to do this, the contribution of different people who work together, such as designers, makers, therapists, doctors, and of course people with disabilities and their caregivers, is required. The method for developing these solutions and the co-design, which OpenDot, thanks to the experience gained through the collaboration with the TOG Foundation, has applied for several years to the world of healthcare. A method able to enable and facilitate processes, stimulate creativity in order to create new solutions and improve the lives of people by generating innovation.

1

LISTEN AND OBSERVE

Co-design means creating a space where all opinions, competences and experiences count and are useful, it means to enact a process based on listening.

5

THINK AND DESIGN TOGETHER

Moments of sharing, exchange and design collective guide the group towards the final idea, stimulating everyone's creativity when it comes to devising new and innovative solutions able to address real needs.

2

TEACH AND LEARN

We are all experts in something and reciprocal training is fundamental: doctors, designers and disabled individuals, experts in their condition, share knowledge and competences, which they intersect.

6

MATERIALIZE THE IDEA

The production of the first prototype thanks to software, digital fabrication technologies and rapid prototyping, allows us to touch, explore, and test the idea. And last but not least, customize it.

3

SPEAK THE SAME LANGUAGE

In order to break down the wall of Englishisms and technicalities of sectorial databases, in favor of a common language that everyone can understand.

7

PROTOTYPE, PROTOTYPE

The prototyping phase is a spiral process and the projects improve with increasing versions, compared to a constant comparison on how to perfect the object.

4

SHARE REAL NEEDS

The object is to resolve a necessary reality, small or large bears no importance, what counts is concentrating on the reason. The "how" comes later.

8

REPLICATE, SCALE, SHARE

A well designed project on it's own could be useful and replicated to also respond to others' needs. Here is where the value of the open source philosophy comes into play: share the process and the final solution is a way to enrich the project and to amplify it's social impact.

APPENDIX 10 // Open Call Questionnaire

Application - Open Health HACKademy 27th September - 6th Oktober 2019

Hi,

Thank you for your interest in the Open Health HACKademy.

It would be great if you could fill out this form as part of your application and send us additional information (CV, portfolio, website links) by email (hackademy@be-able.info). This makes it more structured and allows us to put together possible teams more easily. To have many or good skills is not a prerequisite for participation, but we ask them to be able to put the teams together better.

—

So that we can assign the form to your application, you can enter your name or alternatively a pseudonym. If you use a pseudonym, please don't forget to mention it when sending us additional information by email.

Regarding data protection you will find here the link to the terms of use of the Google form (<https://policies.google.com/terms?hl=de&gl=de=en&gl=en>).

* **Erforderlich**

1. Name or pseudonym *

2. Your email address *

3. What is your motivation to participate in the Open Health HACKademy? Do you already have a connection to the topic? *

4. What do you want to gain from the event? What do you want to learn? What do you want to create? *

In which languages do you feel safe to work in a team?
Wählen Sie alle zutreffenden Antworten aus.

- german
- english

What experience and skills do you have?

6. Experience in the health sector *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
a little	<input type="radio"/>	a lot				

7. Electronics / Soldering *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
beginner	<input type="radio"/>	professional				

8. textile / sewing *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
beginner	<input type="radio"/>	professional				

9. coding / programing *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
beginner	<input type="radio"/>	professional				

10. graphics & visualization *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
beginner	<input type="radio"/>	professional				

11. video editing & filming *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
beginner	<input type="radio"/>	professional				

12. Fabrication Technologies (3D Printing / Lasercutting /CNC Milling etc.) *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
beginner	<input type="radio"/>	professional				

13. 3D Modelling / CAD *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
beginner	<input type="radio"/>	professional				

14. Experience with collaborative teamwork? *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
beginner	<input type="radio"/>	professional				

15. Experience with project management

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
beginner	<input type="radio"/>	professional				

16. Any other skills you would like to name?

Projects

Which project would you like to participate in and how would you like to get involved?

17. My favorite project is... *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- Case - Footbike - with Sven Kocar
- Case - Wheelchair Joystick - with Jonas Morgenroth
- Case - E-Scooter for wheelchair users - with Adina Hermann

18. Please describe briefly what you find particularly appealing about your first choice and how you think you can get involved. *

19. What other projects can you imagine to participating in? *

Wählen Sie alle zutreffenden Antworten aus.

- Case - Footbike - with Sven Kocar
- Case - Wheelchair Joystick - with Jonas Morgenroth
- Case - E-Scooter for wheelchair users - with Adina Hermann

Teamtypes

We make sure that the team mix is as good as possible, so please give us your opinion: Which of the following team types can you identify with the most?

If you are not sure of your type you can make an online-test (dt.) of the Belbin-Teamtypes:

<https://www.123test.de/Teamrollentest/>

20. Which 3 team types suits you best? *

Wählen Sie alle zutreffenden Antworten aus.

- SHAPER – I like to challenge the team to improve, questioning norms, and finding the best approaches to problems. Obstacles are exciting Challenger. Sometimes I'm too argumentative and I may offend people's feelings.
- IMPLEMENTER – I get things done and turn the team's ideas and concepts into practical actions and plans. I work systematically, efficiently and well organized. On the downside, I may be inflexible and somewhat resistant to change.
- COMPLETER-FINISHER – I do care for that projects are completed thoroughly. I'm concerned with deadlines and will push the team to make sure the job is completed on time. I'm orderly, conscientious and anxious. Sometimes though I may worry unnecessarily and find it hard to delegate.
- COORDINATOR – I like to guide the team to the objectives. I'm a good listener and I easily recognize the value that each team members brings to the table. I'm calm and can delegate tasks effectively. My potential weaknesses are that I may delegate away too much personal responsibility, and may tend to be manipulative
- TEAM WORKER – I like to provide support and make sure the team is working together. I'm flexible, diplomatic, and perceptive. I prioritize team cohesion and helping people getting along. My weaknesses may be a tendency to be indecisive, and maintain uncommitted positions during discussions and decision-making.
- RESOURCE INVESTIGATOR – I'm innovative and curious. I like to explore all available options, develop contacts, and negotiate for resources on behalf of the team. I'm more the outgoing and extroverted type. On the downside, I may lose enthusiasm quickly, and I'm sometimes overly optimistic.
- THE PLANT – I easily come up with new ideas and approaches. I thrive on praise but criticism is hard for me to deal with. I'm more the introverted type and prefer to work apart from the team. I'm a poor communicators and tend to ignore given parameters and constraints.
- EVALUATER – I'm best at analyzing and evaluating ideas that other people come up with. I'm objective and carefully weigh the pros and cons of all the options before I come to a decision. I'm strategic in my approach. But I'm a poor motivator and tend to react rather than instigating events.
- SPECIALISTS – I have specialized knowledge that is needed to get the job done. I'm proud on my skills and abilities and within a team I prefer to commit myself fully to my field of expertise. Sometimes this may limit my contribution, and lead to a preoccupation with technicalities at the expense of the bigger picture.

Thank you for your application!

We would also like to ask you to send us further information about you (CV, portfolio, website links) with your name (pseudonym) by email. You can also send us questions about the Open Health

<h2>Point of View</h2>	<p>Quote (what I said)</p>
<p>Userportrait Be visual!</p>	<p>What I need..</p> <p>What I don't need..</p>
<p>User/Nutzer My name is.., I do.., I like.., I believe.</p>	<p>Insight Which deeper needs lie behind the obvious?</p>

Inspired by the d.school HPI
Potsdam

 Open Health
HACKademy

Point of View: Best printed in A3. Can be used as a framework to set a focus for the project that is based on a clarified need of the user.

Feedback Grid

Idea Name: _____

<p>What didn't work?/Testee(s) didn't like</p>	
<p>New Ideas</p>	

Feedback is gold! Do not take it personally if someone criticizes the idea and do not defend the idea! Listen closely to your testee(s) and ask "Why?" To understand in detail what is meant.

Inspired by the d.school HPI
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Feedback Grid: Best printed in A3. Can be used as a framework to collect feedback while testing prototypes.

Elaborated by:

Idea Napkin

1. What's the idea?

Give your idea a name and describe it in one sentence!

2. For whom did you develop this idea?

Describe the user and his needs (adapted P.O.V.)?

3 How does your idea work?

Describe the main function and 2-3 features. Make a drawing!

4. What still needs to be clarified?

What is still unclear, what information is needed, what could be the next steps?

APPENDIX 12 // Team Process Templates from HACKademy

Team Member Profile: Best printed in A4. Provides a framework to support the getting to know each other process in the team. When displayed in the workspace of the Team it also helps any supporter like a coach or Mentor to know more about the Team.

HI! My name is:

- Passionate about:
- Background:
- Transformative experience:
- Favorite food:

...and MY TALENTS are:

I want my team to know...

About me (What do you like or dislike while working in team)

Introvert Extrovert

About my life obligations (What I need to do beside the HACKademy)

Portrait

Open Health
HACKademy

APPENDIX 13 // Healthcare co-design toolkit

USE THIS SPACE FOR DRAWING, SKETCHING, USABILITY STUDIES ETC.

TEAM NAME

TEAM MEMBERS

NEED

Describe your project in a tweet (140–280 characters)
Describe the need in 500–750 characters. Suggestion: Check the interview tool for reference and ask yourself: Why is it important for the user? Who is the person with need? What is the action to be enabled? Where is the solution more needed? When is the solution more needed?

CONCEPT

Describe your project in a tweet (140–280 characters)

1. HOW TO DEFINE THE CONCEPT

This template is part of the co-design for healthcare toolkit, by OpenDot Fab Lab. The toolkit will be available online under CC BY-NC-SA soon on www.opendotlab.it

TEAM	_____
DATE	_____

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*** empathy (n)**

the ability to share someone else's feelings or experiences by imagining what it would be like to be in that person's situation.

INTRO

Good design requires empathy* for the people you are designing for, because their need is rarely your own. To empathize, you engage with people trying to understand: who they are, their values, their thoughts, what is important to them. And the easiest way is to speak to them, building up a positive dialogue.

How to make a positive dialogue is the tool to enable you to connect with people, it is an opportunity to hear them describing their experiences in their own words. This is the tool which guides you to:

- Get to know the people you are designing for
- Keep people at the center of your research (Human Centered Design)
- Help people freely express their own needs
- Uncover needs that people have, which they may or may not be aware of
- Focus on real needs rather than desires
- Frame a feasible need
- Produce a clear and common vision on the concept

At the end of the interview, you can precisely define the need, which will become the new point of reference for the next phases: a need that is not fully understood it is difficult to be met.

THE EMPATHIZER ATTITUDE

- Be curious // Keep an open mind, approach this design challenge afresh and see the wonder.
- Ask questions // Even when you think you already know the answers, question everything to learn about user perception.
- You may be surprised by the answers.
- Forget everything // Don't carry assumptions that are based on your previous experiences, your understanding or expertise may lead you to misconceptions and stereotypes about disabilities.
- Never judge // Just observe and engage users without the influence of value judgments upon their actions, circumstances, decisions, or "issues."
- Listen // Really. This tool is a path but you can always leave the familiar and

2. HOW TO CREATE POSITIVE DIALOGUE

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HOW TO MAKE AN INTERVIEW FOR EMPATHY

Step 1: Prepare

Define the role of all team members (i.e. interviewer, note-taker)

Environment deeply influences people's behavior:

- don't sit in front of the person with needs like a panel of judges
- avoid hospital stereotypes as medical charts or technical language

Respect the other's experience and role:

- the designer shouldn't argue about the need's utility, reality or importance
- the designer shouldn't argue about the personal aesthetic taste of the user: if he likes it pink, then let's make it pink
- the person with need shouldn't argue the feasibility/complexity of a project

Help a nice and smooth creative process:

- if you feel that the user is embarrassed or uncomfortable, back off and don't insist. Search for the info you need in another way
- if you feel that the user has unrealistic, too high expectations, talk about it. Time and resources are limited, and we have to consider that
- if you feel that the user has unclear ideas about its need, help him/her to clarify it (when do you use it? to do what? where? what if we start focussing only on this context...)
- don't be aggressive and let the person finish thinking and talking. Wait a bit if needed.

Set reasonable goals:

- the user has a need and the hope you (and technologies) can do everything: be gentle and explain that you are all working together with the aim of getting to a final object and that this object might not be what they are imagining you have two weeks to define, design, develop, make and share a working solution, plan things realistically.

Consider the "lost-in-translation" effect:

- people with need are not native English speaker and they may lack proper words to talk about their disabilities.
- they may not feel comfortable enough to tell their personal background and knowledge in that specific situation: be kind and respectful

Step 2: Interview

Introduce yourself (3-4 sentences): it's always nice to know a bit about the people we talk to. Say something about your skills as well. For "non-designers" it may be useful to have a visualization of ideas, such as images, materials, sketches while proceeding with the collection of information.

A simple list of possible questions (use if as inspirational, don't ask all of them!):

Introduction

- What is your name?
- Can you tell a bit about yourself?

Interest

- Have you ever taken part in such events like hackathons or co-design sessions?
- What is your interest in this initiative? What do you think it is going to happen during this summer school?
- Have you ever built something for your own need?

Need

- Which is the action to be enabled?
- How did the need come about? where does the difficulty occur? (i.e. at the restaurant, at school, ...)
- Why is it a problem?
- Which actions are possible?
- Considering the aids or what you are currently using, can you figure out what you would need to better make the action/movement? What would enable you to make it easily?
- In which circumstances do you need a spoon? (i.e. eating a soap/ice cream) What is the precise action you're interested in doing? (i.e. eating alone, eating in a restaurant, eating with colleagues, etc.)? In which context/environment? (ie. at the seaside, in the office, at home) " It helps to narrow possibilities.
- If you are the caregiver of the user ask how you figured that out and when it is most likely to have an impact.

Aesthetics

- What do you like? How important is for you a beautiful object (i.e. its color)? "What about functionality?" you may ask. Don't forget that we are human and beauty is the lever that makes the difference between "I have it" and "I

use it".

- Beyond aspects related to both the need and type of disability, while brainstorming, take into consideration personal taste and beliefs like environmental choices (i.e. against disposable products or objects made of plastic), cultural/gender/religious issues (i.e. against pink as a girly color), food...

Tips and tricks about language style and behaviour:

- Make sure to write down exactly what the person says not what you think they might mean, hearing exactly what people are saying
- Ask confirmation of what you have written down, just to make sure you understand correctly. i.e. "Let me make sure I've got this right, you mean..."
- Be friendly and willing, so that the person feels comfortable to say "no" or "I don't agree"
- Construct the sentence using positive tense or "encouraging" verbs i.e. "it helps" it's better than "it lacks" Ask "why?" (i.e. "why to you is more important to be able to have dinner in a restaurant then lunch with colleagues?") because what users want and need can be different and inconsistencies may hide interesting insights
- Ask questions neutrally and don't suggest answers
- Ask questions regarding disability or other related issues as it is normal to have no direct experience or knowledge of anything. Use polite expressions such as "I am sorry but what do you mean with...?"
- Don't be afraid of asking or talking
- Be aware of body language and emotions as they represent not verbal clues
- Have fun! Even when things get serious, it is important to always remember to laugh and celebrate results and good talking
- In case of tension, you can change the topic, and even stand up or have a break at the coffee station

Step 3: Conclusion

- Collect all thoughts and considerations, setting off from a broad perspective and gradually getting into more and more detail
- Review the answers to the questions and prioritize the information: what is important? Why?
- Reframe and rewrite the initial need

- Frame the need description with brief, clear, precise sentences
- Frame the concept description with brief, clear, precise sentences

The final result of this process is the NEED definition:

- Define the need using these questions as a guideline. your objective is to understand clearly what the real need is.
- Why is it important for the user? (he/she wants to be independent on/more productive) > it's important to understand the real motivation behind the requests, and it helps to stay focused on the user's need
- Who is the person with need? (he/she a child, an adult, an elder, etc.) > different ages, sex, believe, groups, etc. affect how to design the solution
- What is the action to be enabled? (it is something to help me to...) > clarify and define what's the action is. > try to narrow down the request. A need well defined is easier to tackle
- Where is the solution more needed? (at the restaurant, at school, at home...)
- When is the solution more needed? (alone, with friends, when he/she goes to bed...) > often similar problems require different approaches based on the context, narrow down the context to better define how to design the solution

A good need should be expressed in one or two sentences at most. It is important to rewrite the phrase describing the need again and again until its intended sense and potential are fully recognized by the entire team.

Gant Chart

You can use a gant chart to set up your workflow. This can be found by scanning the QR code below.

3. HOW TO ORGANISE WORKFLOW

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PROJECT TITLE

Product Name + Value Proposition (60 characters)

SUBTITLE

Your project in a tweet (280 characters)

CORE FEATURES

List your core features, pick the main 3 and circle the topmost (only one!)
Alert! Do consider if your features properly correspond to the target audience(s).

MAIN IMAGE

Paste it or sketch it.

Tips: include a human, some action, mystery, within a nice composition.

TARGET

List the target audience(s) your project is designed for (with priorities if it has multiple targets.)

4. HOW TO COMMUNICATE THE PROJECT

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USER EXPERIENCE

Describe the UX of your project by sketching the main actions and writing a short sentence related to them.

Tips: first image is usually to show the premise of the project, the context or the stand-by situation; the second is to communicate the interaction and last its effect.

ABSTRACT

Describe your project with 500 characters.

Tips: include the purpose, the target, the core feature, the method and the result.

Tips: each frame is about 7/8 seconds, take realistic lifestyle shots, include call to action if needed, voiceover is always helpful, nice music get people captivated.

Suggestions: 2 frames for the overview + 2 frames explaining the vision + 4 frames to demonstrate the core features + 4 frames showing team and/or process + 4 frames to deep dive the project and UX (Copy this page if more space is needed).

ACTION _____
AUDIO _____

ACTION _____
AUDIO _____

ACTION _____
AUDIO _____

5. HOW TO MAKE A STORYBOARD

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PREPARING DOCUMENTATION INTRODUCTION

Documentation, why?

No matter how complex the project is, documentation is very important! And everyone involved is expected to contribute to it!

With proper documentation, you can understand, remember, share and replicate. Furthermore, nice and clear documentation is the best business card to present your project and yourself to the world! Open or community-based projects need nice and clear documentation to reach users, contributors, and even partners or clients. It's also the way we use to increase the impact or the solution, otherwise limited to a very small number of people (sometimes only the one you co-designed with!)

Documentation, when?

You should document while you go! Take pictures and notes of all the steps.

Did you stumble on a mistake or a bug? Did you reach a milestone? Have you discovered a new feature? Are you setting up a machine? Are you preparing your materials?

You can filter and take away useless steps later on, but if you don't record everything it might happen you have to redo some parts only to be able to take pictures of it.

Documentation, how?

There are many ways to document a project, each one fitting for a specific scope. The best way to share a Careable is a tutorial: keep in mind you're trying to help someone you don't know, and you can't talk to, to replicate what you did. That's the right mindset! Give instruction, suggestions, tips; explain why you decided to do something, link the material you learned from, share parameters, files (both in a universally accessible format, such as .STL, and editable files, such as .3dm). Talk about successes, bugs, and mistakes, conclusions, and developments.

Documentation, what?

Documentation is made of:

- Texts: where you explain your goals, how you reached them and what conclusions you gained.
- Media: that is made of pictures, clips and other means to show your project steps.
- Files: that comprise the digital materials you used to make your project and want to share

The easier way to do a comprehensible tutorial is to think about a recipe: description at the beginning, ingredients, tools needed, and then a set of instruction with pictures and video as support. Even if you have to do more than one thing at the same time (while the oven is warming up, chop the potatoes), instruction is always in a precise order. It's important to simplify the process as much as possible!

Whenever you're stuck with your documentation, try to mimic someone else style if you don't know yet what's your own and always put yourselves in the situation where you have to choose overabundant material instead of recreating. From Instructables to Github, spend some time looking for some topics of your interest. They're full of inspiration and resources!

Tips

- Keep a camera or a smartphone at hand's reach
- Memorize the screen-capture commands of your system
- Always take note of what's happening.
- Not everything might end in your final documentation, but it's much better cherrypicking from surplus material than to re-create old scenarios
- Recording clips or GIFs in quite easy and a very efficient way to describe steps of your work.
- Use dedicated applications such as Gyazo, OBS or Greenshot to do so
- Report (briefly) issues as well instead of omitting them, people encountering the same problem will be eternally thankful for that

DOCUMENTATION: TEXT

Generally, your documentation will feature a good portion of written text, hence a good exposition of your project

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6. SHARING THE PROJECT ONLINE

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DATE _____

heavily relies on it. Ideally, a documentation text should describe solely the journey from state A to B, and how you did so.

- Use a simple language, avoid acronyms, codes, and tech vocabulary if possible if you have to use those terms, explain the meaning with an extra sentence or a link
- Use short paragraphs
- Avoid metaphors and fancy rhetoric
- Make use of bullet-list and enumerations
- Always mention external references and contributions
- Don't use files names such as "ThatImage_final003_reallyFinal.png". Even file names help to understand
- Silly fonts, unformatted texts and broken files can ruin the authority of the best projects.
- Keep it all simple and clean!

DOCUMENTATION: FILES

Your project will surely involve a certain amount of digital files: CADs, CAMs, drawings, codes, models, logs, spreadsheets and so on. Whatever is essential for describing and replicating your project must be included in your documentation, in its latest version.

- Don't use working files unless you're using them for reporting a bug or a setup test
- Name your files in the most appropriate and concise manner
- Always use files formats that are cross-platform, standardized and ubiquitous
- You can upload ALSO proprietary formats to simplify the editing

Common formats are PNG or JPG for 2D raster images, SVG or DXF for vectorial, STL or OBJ for 3D CADs: add the source proprietary file too, if it helps to edit/modify/adjust the project Code: Use the proprietary file, usually it's readable by a notepad app.

DOCUMENTATION: MEDIA

Pictures

Taking pictures of the making of your projects is crucial, because pictures help comprehension, interrupts lengthy readings, and because people often will skim through your presentation and only look at them. There's nothing bad about it and good pictures actually will entice readers to know more about what they've just seen.

- Take pictures with a neutral background, good diffuse light and as clean as possible (extra cables, tools, parts, etc. can make the pictures

incomprehensible)

- No blurred, burned or dark pictures!
- 1280x800 pixels is usually enough, rarely you need something larger than 1920x1080 pixels Prefer horizontal orientation (landscape)
- JPG or PNG is usually ok
- Screenshots are very useful
- You can find online some tips for good pictures.

Graphics

Graphics are generally a good way to deliver and boil-down many informations in a concise and intuitive way. Don't underestimate the usefulness of charts, infographics and schemes - even with minimal stylization or just captured from a hand-drawn sketch - but still save yourself some room to describe them. There's a whole study field dedicated to this topic (and countless toolsets) so don't break your head too much if you can't find the best way to depict your information. Just picture in your mind what you want to express and render it in the simplest graphical form you can, or ask for help to someone with more experience than you in graphic design. If you're dealing with vectorial images, be sure to save the files in plain SVG format and always check the result (softwares such as Adobe Illustrator might add some file overhead). If you go for PDFs, check the version and be sure to resolve any conversion issue (invisible layers, fonts, link, etc).

Video

Videos can be a double-edged sword. A simple smartphone with camera will obliterate the need of explaining difficult steps, but relying on lengthy videos or using low-quality content can ruin the best intentions.

- Video must be brief, steady and clear
- Very often it's enough to have a still camera
- Video editing is time consuming, limit it to the minimum (unless you love it!)
- Light is crucial: bright, diffuse, homogeneous Prefere horizontal orientation (landscape)

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